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Employment in Innovative Companies in Italian Regions

It grew by an average of 20.03% from 2018 to 2023.

The European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) calculates the value of employment in innovative companies in Italian regions. This indicator is a ratio between the number of employees in innovative companies and the total employment for companies with 10 or more employees. Innovative companies are defined as those that have introduced an innovation or engage in any type of innovation activity. Innovation in companies has a profound impact on worker employability, but its effect in companies oriented towards product and process innovation varies from region to region. Business innovation is particularly important during a period of economic recession. The data refers to the twenty Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Employment in Innovative Companies in Italian Regions in 2023. Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, and Veneto emerge as undisputed leaders in employment in innovative companies, with numbers exceeding 150 points. On the contrary, regions such as Molise, Basilicata, and Sicily show the lowest values in terms of employment in innovative companies, reflecting a more complex and challenging reality. These regions, often characterized by a lower degree of industrialization and a lower density of research and development infrastructures, face significant obstacles in promoting innovation. The scarcity of direct investments in these territories can be seen both as a consequence and a cause of limited innovative activity, creating a difficult cycle to break without targeted and substantial interventions. Moreover, the gap between Northern and Southern Italy is clearly highlighted by this data. While the North continues to expand its innovative capacity, the South struggles to keep up. This discrepancy underscores the need for tailored regional policies that can incentivize the creation and development of innovative companies even in less advanced regions. Such policies could include tax incentives for startups, increased investments in technological infrastructures, and training and skills development programs for the local workforce. A strength that emerges from the data analysis is the potential inherent in regions with average employment, such as Friuli Venezia Giulia, Tuscany, and Trentino Alto Adige. These regions show high employment values in innovative companies thanks to a series of effective policies that have been able to attract investments and promote research and development. The existence of technology hubs and industrial districts, along with a network of universities and research centers, contributes to a favorable environment for innovation.

Employment in Innovative Companies in Italian Regions between 2018 and 2023. The growth in employment in regions like Puglia, which saw the highest percentage increase (+56.60%), testifies to

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the effectiveness of innovation incentive policies that have transformed the local economic fabric. Similarly, Emilia-Romagna and Lombardy, with substantial increases both in absolute and percentage terms, continue to consolidate their position as pivotal centers of Italian innovation, thanks to an environment that fosters integration between universities, research centers, and industries. However, these values also shed light on the difficulties encountered in other areas. Regions such as Molise and Sicily have shown a significant decline, with Molise recording the largest percentage decrease (-29.95%). These data are concerning and raise questions about the nature of the obstacles preventing these regions from fully exploiting their innovation potential. These could include the lack of adequate infrastructures, deficiencies in the education system that fail to produce the skills required by innovative companies, or poor collaboration between the public and private sectors. The case of Valle d'Aosta, with a slight decrease, further highlights how even regions with smaller populations and limited economic potentials can suffer from a lack of targeted innovation strategies. This indicates the need for a more personalized approach in economic development policies, which not only consider regional differences but also specific local opportunities and challenges. The evident disparity between the North and South of the country is another critical point. While Northern Italy continues to develop and attract significant investments in high-tech sectors, the South struggles to keep pace. This imbalance not only limits national growth possibilities but also accentuates socio-economic inequalities between regions. To address these challenges, public policies must be designed to incentivize innovation in a balanced and inclusive manner. Tax incentives for startups, increased investments in research and development, advanced training programs, and the promotion of partnerships between universities and industry are just some of the interventions that can help stimulate employment in innovative companies throughout Italy.

Employment in Innovative Companies in Italian Macro-Regions between 2018 and 2023. All three Italian macro-regions showed growth in employment in innovative companies during the analyzed period. This indicates a generally positive trend for the country's innovation sector. The North shows substantial growth both in absolute and percentage terms, with an increase of 25.90 units and a percentage of 23.95%. This suggests that the North continues to be the engine of Italian innovation, supported by a robust ecosystem that includes a high density of technologically advanced industries, research and development centers, and relatively better access to venture capital. The Center recorded the highest percentage increase of 32.86%, with an absolute increase of 32.34 units. This impressive jump could be attributed to the growing importance of cities like Rome and Florence in the innovation landscape, where the interaction between universities, public institutions, and private companies has created fertile ground for the growth of innovative companies. The South saw the most modest growth, both in absolute terms (+5.61) and percentage terms (+6.96%). This increase, although positive, indicates that the South is growing at a slower pace compared to the rest of the country. This region may be limited by various structural factors, such as lower investments in R&D, less developed infrastructures, and more limited access to funding and resources, which together hinder its ability to attract and support innovative companies. These data can serve as a wake-up call for policymakers, highlighting the need to formulate and implement regional strategies that can encourage and support innovation in a more balanced way. For the South, for example, it would be crucial to implement policies that improve access to funding, strengthen technological infrastructures, and promote collaborations between universities and industry. For the Center and North, the focus could be on maintaining and expanding existing capacities, ensuring that the environment remains favorable for innovation and entrepreneurship.

North-South Divide. The data on employment in innovative companies in Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 highlights a significant divide between the North, Center, and South. While the North and Center show strong growth both in absolute and percentage terms, with the North recording a 23.95% increase and the Center even 32.86%, the South shows more modest growth of 6.96%. These numbers reflect the persistent challenges in the South in terms of economic development and innovation, underscoring the need for targeted policies that promote greater territorial equity. Investments in technological infrastructures, education, and training can play a crucial role in stimulating innovation in the South, reducing the gap with other regions, and contributing to a more cohesive and competitive national economic fabric.

Economic Policies to Increase Employment in Innovative Companies in Italian Regions. To increase employment in innovative companies in Italian regions, the following economic policies should be implemented:

- **Tax Relief:** reducing the tax burden for startups and innovative SMEs can incentivize the creation and expansion of these companies. This could include tax deductions on R&D investments, tax credits for hiring qualified personnel, and tax reductions for reinvestments in innovative activities.
- **Subsidized Financing:** providing access to financing at advantageous rates through regional or national funds specifically for innovative companies. These funds could support both the startup phase and the expansion phase.
- **Investments in Broadband and Digital Technologies:** improving access to high-speed internet, particularly in less developed regions, to facilitate innovation and the operation of companies in the technology sector.
- **Technology Hubs and Incubators:** promoting the creation of technology clusters and business incubators that can act as catalysts for innovation and attract new companies and talents.
- **Targeted Training Programs:** investing in training and retraining programs to align the workforce's skills with the needs of innovative companies. This could include partnerships between universities, technical institutes, and companies to ensure a constant flow of qualified talents.
- **Promotion of Entrepreneurship:** encouraging both young and older individuals to pursue entrepreneurial paths through courses, workshops, and seminars that offer practical and theoretical knowledge about startup and innovation dynamics.
- **Bureaucratic Simplification:** reducing bureaucracy for the creation of new companies, especially those with high technological content, to accelerate startup times and reduce initial operating costs.
- **Legislation on Venture Capital and Investments:** modifying regulations to attract more investments from venture capital funds, including incentives for investors who choose to focus on less developed regions.
- **International Networks:** facilitating the integration of Italian innovative companies into international networks and projects, to enable knowledge exchange, access to new markets, and attraction of foreign investments.
- **Localized Support:** adapting support policies based on the economic and productive specificities of each region, for example, strengthening the most promising or already growing sectors in certain areas.

Conclusions. The value of employment in innovative companies grew by an average of 20.03% between 2018 and 2023, increasing from 95.21 units to 114.28 units. However, there are also regions where the value of employment in innovative companies decreased during the period between 2018 and 2023, namely: Valle d'Aosta with -6.12%, Sardinia with -10.72%, Basilicata with -18.63%, Sicily with -24.09%, and Molise with -74.98%. The reduction in these regions is even more severe, especially because the absolute value of employment in innovative companies in these areas was already below average. Therefore, there has been a further weakening of employment performance in regions that were already lagging, manifesting an evident recessionary effect. Looking at macro-regions, we can see a growth in the value of employment in innovative companies. Specifically, the value of employment in innovative companies grew in Southern Italy by 6.96% between 2018 and 2023, in Northern Italy by 23.95%, and in Central Italy by 32.86%. However, while Northern and Central Italy tend to converge, Southern Italy lags behind. This results in employment levels in innovative companies in Southern Italy being significantly lower compared to the Central-Northern regions.

Declarations

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Appendix

